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EDIGITAL SILK ROAD AND SUSTAINABLE TOURISM: ANALYZING THE ADAPTATION OF CHINESE DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This paper discusses the opportunities and obstacles of using Chinese digital tourism platforms to create sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan, within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the Digital Silk Road. As China and Uzbekistan advance their relationship to form an all-weather comprehensive strategic partnership, the exportation of China's mature digital tourism models presents both opportunities and challenges. The paper examines the institutional, technological and cultural frictions in this process. Based on policy transfer theory and institutional isomorphism, the study performs a comparative analysis of policy texts and case studies of Chinese mobile applications such as Ctrip, Fliggy and Alipay. The results indicate that main sources of friction are regulatory discrepancies in digital payments, infrastructural gaps, and the necessity for localized operational strategies. The paper concludes by suggesting optimization directions for sustainable Sino-Uzbek digital tourism collaboration, emphasizing standards harmonization, infrastructure investment, and effective data governance.

Keywords: Digital Silk Road, Sustainable Tourism, Digital Platforms, Policy Transfer, Belt and Road Initiative, Uzbekistan.

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between China and Uzbekistan, which has been further strengthened into an all-weather comprehensive strategic partnership in a new era in January 2024, has already prepared a fertile ground of the extensive cooperation, especially within the frames of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and its digital version, the Digital Silk Road (DSR). At the same time, Uzbekistan has already started an extensive national policy of becoming a regional tourist giant, and the strategy of the country "Uzbekistan-2030" will help it rise to unprecedented tourist attraction and tourist income (UZDaily, 2026). One of the key facilitators of this vision is the digital transformation which is expected to streamline the efficiency of services and the experiences of the tourists and facilitate the sustainable expansion of the sector (OECD, 2025).

With China coming up with one of the most developed digital ecosystems in the world, it presents a powerful example of digital tourism. Its domestic tourism environment has been transformed by platforms, such as Ctrip (Trip.com), Fliggy, and mobile payment giants Alipay and WeChat Pay. The viability and sustainability of applying such Chinese mature digital solutions to the Uzbek market is the main issue this paper will solve. Although its potential is enormous, the institutional friction and challenge of adapting to the process has been enormous, touching legal frameworks, technological infrastructure and even social-cultural norms. In the given work, the conflict under

consideration is as follows: does the transplantation of the Chinese model of digital tourism experience some sort of rejection when faced with the national specificities of Uzbekistan?

The study will have three main purposes. To begin with, the research aims to discover the critical forces and impediments in the transfer of digital tourism policies and platforms between China and Uzbekistan. Second, it assesses the flexibility of the certain models of Chinese mobile applications within the Uzbek market. Third, it offers solutions to reduce the challenges and maximize towards sustainable development. Theoretically, the paper is an addition to the body of policy transfer, digital governance, and sustainable tourism literature since it presents theoretical concepts to a new context Digital Silk Road. In a practical sense, it offers practical suggestions to the Uzbek policymakers to utilize the foreign digital expertise and to the Chinese tech enterprises to enhance their activities in the Central Asia.

The following are the research questions that are used in this study:

- (1) What are the main policy and institutional conditions that ease or obstruct the Chinese digital tourism models transfer to the Uzbekistan?
- (2) How do Chinese online travel agencies and mobile payment systems respond to the local regulatory and market environment in Uzbekistan?
- (3) How to optimize the Sino-Uzbek digital tourism cooperation to improve its sustainability?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Policy Transfer Theory

Policy transfer is the process where knowledge of policies, administrative arrangements, institutions and ideas in political setting (in the past or present) is applied in policy, administrative arrangements, institutional and idea development in a different political setting (Dolowitz and Marsh, 2000). Dolowitz and Marsh model offers an extensive approach to the study of this process in which the following questions are posed: Why do actors transfer policies? Who are the key actors? What is transferred? What are the sources of the lessons? Which are the various levels of transfer? What limits the process of policy transfer? And what is the relationship between the process of policy transfer and policy success and failure? The transfer of policies in the Digital Silk Road is frequently driven by both a voluntary learning process, in which countries such as Uzbekistan take initiative to study successful examples to be emulated, and a forceful one based on the technical requirements and the network effects of the leading digital platforms. Stone (2012) goes further to explain the difference between hard transfer of certain policies and soft transfer of ideas and norms, where the latter is frequently more common in the situation of international development.

Institutional Isomorphism Theory

Institutional isomorphism refers to the nature of institutional organizations to be more similar as time progresses (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). This convergence occurs in three processes. Coercive isomorphism is caused by pressure exerted by other organizations and the state, including the adaptation to the laws of data security, or international standards. Mimetic isomorphism is where organizations emulate other successful organizations to decrease uncertainty such as an Uzbek OTA copying Ctrip. Professionalization and spread of norms e.g. use of international standards of digital payments motivate normative isomorphism. This can be applied to the Chinese digital models being absorbed by Uzbekistan as it is both an attempt to imitate the winning approaches and a process of being sensitive to the norms and standards ingrained in Chinese technology and capital.

Digital Platforms and Sustainable Tourism

Digital platforms are becoming more central to the tourism sector serving as mediators between travelers and an enormous number of services, including accommodation and transportation, as well as local experiences (Zeqiri et al., 2025). They can also be potent agents of sustainable tourism because they maximize the utilization of the resources, give small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) a chance to operate in remote places and provide a more effective way to regulate the tourist flow with the purpose of preventing over-tourism. The World Bank (2018) has identified the transformative nature of the digital platform in the developing economies, whereby the platform can

lower the cost of doing business as well as increase market access to the local providers of the services. Nevertheless, digital platform role is complicated. The prevalence of the large Online Travel Agencies (OTAs) may also result in value extraction, the marginalization of the local businesses not being digital savvy, and the imposition of the new burden on local infrastructure.

METHOD

The research design that will be used in this study is qualitative in terms of policy document analysis and comparative case study approach. The research approach will deconstruct the convoluted relationship between policy, technology, and local environment in the export of digital tourism models between China and Uzbekistan.

Phase 1: Policy Text Analysis. The initial one is a systematic review and analysis of major policy documents of the two countries. In the case of China, such policies are the Belt and Road Initiative, the Digital Silk Road and the creation of Smart Tourism. In the case of Uzbekistan, the strategy of analysis is the Digital Uzbekistan-2030, the Concept of the Development of the Tourism Sector in 2019-2025, and the appropriate laws including the laws on payments and personal data.

Phase 2: Comparative Case Study. The second stage employs the multi-case study method in order to empirically analyse the suitability of Chinese mobile applications in Uzbekistan. The cases involved in the selection are important components of the digital tourism system: Online Travel Agencies (OTAs) including Ctrip and Fliggy, and Cross-Border Payments systems including Alipay and WeChat Pay. The case study information is based on publicly available sources, such as the company reports, news article, industry analysis, and user reviews.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The discussion indicates that there is a lot of policy resonance in the desire by China to export its digital standards through DSR and the urgency of Uzbekistan to undergo digital transformation of its tourism industry. Nevertheless, this policy alignment at the upper level does not translate into the success of Chinese digital platforms on the ground due to various points of friction.

Tourism Development Context

The Uzbekistan nation has shown tremendous expansion in the number of international tourists in the last decade. The country received 8 million foreign tourists in 2024, which is a multiplication of the number of visitors that were about 1 million in the year 2016. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 only slightly disrupted this growth curve, but the industry has proven to be highly resilient and recovered. The strategic nature of the tourism industry in the country is highlighted by the fact that the government has set a very ambitious project to bring 15-20 million visitors to the country by 2030.

Figure 1: International Tourist Arrivals in Uzbekistan (2016-2024)

Policy and Regulatory Friction

One of the main problems is to operate within the regime of Uzbekistan. Although the strategy of the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 embraces the use of foreign technology, there are certain laws that cause obstacles. As an example, the Law on Payments and Payment Systems in the Uzbekistan require extremely strict conditions to license and conduct operations as a foreign electronic money system, which will be a barrier to Alipay and WeChat Pay entering the country. Likewise, the needs of data localization which require that personal information of citizens should be stored on servers in Uzbekistan is problematic to global platforms that were designed with centralized data centres.

Figure 2: Framework for Digital Platform Adaptation in Cross-Border Tourism Cooperation

Platform Digitalization and Local Adaptation

The case study of the OTAs such as Ctrip and Fliggy that we conducted shows the disconnect between the capabilities of the platform and the local preparedness. These platforms are highly effective in serving Chinese outbound tourists but their performance in Uzbekistan is limited by the level of digitalization among the merchants in Uzbekistan. A vast number of smaller hotels, tour operator, and restaurants do not have digital tools and capabilities to fit into these large-scale platforms. Another obstacle to the onboarding process and customer service is the language barriers.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Chinese Digital Platform Adaptation in Uzbekistan

Platform Category	Chinese Platform	Key Function	Adaptation Challenges
OTA	Ctrip, Fliggy	Booking flights, hotels, tours	Limited digital readiness of local SMEs; Language barriers
Payment	Alipay, WeChat Pay	Mobile payments for tourists	Strict licensing requirements; Lack of POS infrastructure
Navigation	Baidu Maps, Amap	Maps and location services	Incomplete mapping data; Lack of real-time information

Figure 3: Comparative Digital Tourism Readiness China vs. Uzbekistan

Infrastructure and Socio-Cultural Gaps

In addition to policy and platform related matters, there are more extensive infrastructure and socio-cultural considerations. Although the internet connectivity in Uzbekistan is getting better, network and speed may be erratic in isolated and hilly areas that are usually some of the major tourism resources. Moreover, the culture of payment that has dominated most of the Uzbekistan continues to be cash-based, which has slowed the uptake of digital payments despite its availability.

Table 2: Key Policy Documents Governing Digital Tourism in China and Uzbekistan

Country	Policy Document	Year	Key Provisions
China	Smart Tourism Development Plan	2017	Big data and mobile internet integration
China	Belt and Road Initiative Action Plan	2015	International digital connectivity
Uzbekistan	Digital Uzbekistan 2030	2020	Digital infrastructure targets
Uzbekistan	Tourism Development Concept	2019	Digital service enhancement
Bilateral	China-Uzbekistan Joint Statement	2024	Strategic partnership provisions

CONCLUSION

The application of the successful digital tourism model of China to the Uzbekistan through the Digital Silk Road is not a copy-pasting exercise. It is a complicated bargaining among a strong, standardized technological paradigm and a local situation. In this paper, it is established that there is congruence between high-level policy goals but high levels of operational, regulatory, and

infrastructural tension. The main issue is to overcome the barrier between the high profiles of Chinese online services and the present level of online preparedness in the tourism sector Uzbekistan is currently in.

In order to create a more sustainable and win-win digital tourism relationship, this paper will provide a multi-pronged optimization path. To begin with, instead of a one-way transfer, both nations ought to take part in a policy learning and co-evolution process by creating a bilateral regulatory tourism sandbox. Second, the Chinese businesses ought to invest in the soft infrastructure such as programs to improve digital literacy of local tourism SMEs. Third, a Chinese Tech + Uzbek Operation is a model that may be more sustainable, whereby the Chinese companies will supply the core technological backbone with the local partners being empowered to run the operations.

This study has several limitations, the first being the use of secondary sources of data and the high rate of dynamism in the digital platform environment and the bilateral policy frameworks. The studies can be improved in the future by the use of primary data in the form of the interviews with the platform operators, local merchants, and policymakers.

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